

WHITE PAPER

Quantum for HPC

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**EUROPEAN TECHNOLOGY
PLATFORM FOR HIGH
PERFORMANCE COMPUTING**

Co-leaders

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	3
Glossary of Acronyms	3
Research trends and current state of the art	4
Challenges	5
Application use cases	5
Benchmarking	5
Software-hardware stack	5
Application and user-related software ...	6
System-related software	6
System integration	7
Emulation of quantum computers with HPC systems	8
R&I priorities	9
Contributing Authors	10

Executive Summary

This is a white paper released as part of the ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda 6.

Quantum computing is a future accelerator for HPC systems. Due to the fact that most algorithms are hybrid quantum-classical the integration of quantum computing needs to be accomplished on all levels of the hardware-software stack, namely on system level, programming level and application level. On application level it is recommended to focus on the integration of quantum computing algorithms in longer HPC work flows. The progress of the application development should form the basis for the definition of application centric benchmarks with the goal to compare different hardware technologies. Increased hardware systems size needs to be taken into account in the software stack at the level of user-related and system-related software, e.g. by developing user interfaces, libraries, high-level programming languages and compilers. To manage the scarce quantum resources HPC system software (scheduling, accounting, authentication, etc.) needs to be adapted. For system integration it is important to take care of hardware specific interconnection networks and connectivity between HPC and quantum computing supporting the integration of quantum devices in HPC centres. As a final point we advise to look into HPC implementations of emulators.

Glossary of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
QC	Quantum Computer
QCS	Quantum Computers and Simulators
QPU	Quantum Processing Unit
QUBO	Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization
R&I	Research & Innovation
SIMD	Single-Instruction-Multiple-Data

Research trends and current state of the art

Quantum computing describes a disruptive way of computing based on the principles of quantum theory with the potential to develop a selection of quantum-accelerated applications. Therefore, the integration of quantum computers and simulators (QCS) in high-performance computing (HPC) systems is the main challenge. From an HPC perspective, QCS will be accelerators to HPC clusters. The EuroHPC JU is meant to acquire and deploy QCS stemming from the European Quantum Flagship and other efforts, which have reached a sufficient degree of maturity to support their deployment and their integration in HPC environments, and to prepare software tools, libraries and applications. As stated in the Quantum Flagship SRIA 2030 (<https://qt.eu/media/pdf/Strategic-Research-and-Industry-Agenda-2030.pdf>) it is necessary to consider all levels of the system stack – from hardware to application – to successfully integrate quantum systems in classical HPC systems.

QCS devices need to be integrated in HPC systems:

- on a system level: QCS technologies need to be integrated in HPC clusters;
- on a programming level: a full hardware-software stack needs to be built;
- on the application level: to investigate QCS' promise of disruptive changes in the complexity of some applications so that compute intensive or intractable problems for HPC might become tractable in the future.

Currently, we see an era of quantum enablement in which no quantum advantage for an industrially relevant application has yet been achieved. The race to scalable error-corrected QC hardware is still open and we will see multiple QCS technologies in use, at least for an intermediate stage of development, with unique features, which need to be taken into account for a successful integration of QCS.

Three application areas are commonly attributed where quantum advantage is likely to be first demonstrated: optimisation, quantum chemistry and quantum machine learning. QCS applications will be hybrid. Therefore, it is paramount to have an effective and efficient integration of QCS systems to realize potential quantum advantages.

There are several options for the integration of HPC and QCS, and these may coexist in the medium term, until it becomes clear which applications have reached a quantum advantage and how their workflows are set up. New challenges concerning the hardware-software stack for the deployment and the emulation of QCS will arise for larger quantum systems. Benchmarks are needed to assess the properties and capabilities of the different technologies.

Education is the cornerstone on which new generations of quantum aware scientists will be trained since quantum computing requires a new approach (or mindset) to application development. This activity is essential for the long-lasting growth of QC usage.

Challenges

Application use cases

For a successful integration of QCS and HPC, applications need to be studied. Hybridization stems from both the algorithmic level (e.g. variational algorithms) but also in the workflow of long-running HPC applications that might only offload certain tasks on QCs to speed up compute intensive parts of the application. The current state of the applications is still evolving and often need to be adapted to different quantum computing technologies. Thus, it is right now a good time for co-design of the hardware, middleware and application layer. While a lot of work has been put into the development of hybrid algorithms, now is the time to start considering longer workflows in which these algorithms will be integrated in and which show a closer resemblance to industrial and academic applications. Therefore, relevant HPC use cases need to be identified for which a quantum advantage is likely. A set of applications will be tested in the upcoming European Quantum Centres of Excellence, but applications beyond this must also be considered when developing middleware and hardware.

Benchmarking

There are different goals for benchmarking from either a vertical or horizontal perspective:

On a vertical level, benchmarking of the QC hardware / software stack starts with a characterization of the qubits, characterization of a workflow-specific overhead, up to

application kernels or application-centric benchmarking. This will measure the evolution of the quality of quantum systems and could be a means to compare different systems and technologies to assess the potential of these systems for quantum advantage.

On a horizontal level, different quantum computing systems are compared with each other, or quantum computing systems are compared with classical systems (cross-platform benchmarking). This is a means of evaluating quantum advantage, which is the holy grail of benchmarking. Although quantum advantage has often been claimed to exist, these claims have often been downplayed by an improvement in classical algorithms for benchmarking.

In addition, benchmarking can have different optimization objectives such as time-to-solution, energy efficiency, and total carbon emissions. Concerning the integration of QCS and HPC in hybrid quantum-classical systems there is a need in how to measure speedups and workflow specific overhead of hybrid approaches to identify best practices for such an integration. At the moment, a few benchmarks, such as the quantum volume, are broadly used. However, to evaluate the quantum systems and guide the user community, a much more extensive benchmarking is needed.

Progress in application development and experimentation should form the basis for the definition of benchmarks, i.e. they will play a crucial role in the hardware-software co-design. Such a co-design approach is essential. It is also important to develop a widely acknowledged ranking system that is mature and flexible enough to accommodate future technological developments. At the current stage it is vital to promote the development of a broad set of (application-centric) benchmarks in close cooperation with the application communities, so that we do not prematurely lock ourselves into a particular technology or algorithm.

Software-hardware stack

The middleware stack for quantum computing can be roughly divided in two main blocks: application/user related software, and system related software. These stacks are entry points for end-users with different levels of expertise in quantum computing, such as domain experts, algorithm developers, and researchers with hardware expertise (such as pulse-level control). Thus, the end-users are heterogeneous and might each have needs in terms of software tools.

The middleware is closely associated with the nature of the quantum processing units (QPUs) themselves. While universal or digital QCs rely on gates with which they can express any logical operation, analog systems are often restricted to solve a representative NP-complete problem. For example, quantum annealers are well suited to solve Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) problems, while Rydberg simulators address graph-related NP complete problems. In order to be used in a more generic way, bridges to less specific problems are required. To realize universal QCs, different technologies (such as transmons or ions amongst others) can be used. Each technology comes with unique features and restrictions that need to be taken into account when implementing realistic quantum circuits. Entanglement between two qubits is possible depending on the specific implementation technology, as it defines the topology of the resulting QPU, limiting the local interconnections between neighbouring qubits.

Another upcoming challenge will be the increases in the QC system size (i.e. the number of qubits), which makes it even more important to provide a mature middleware for the users, so that the complexity of the actual hardware is hidden from algorithm and application developers. Here more research is needed on a compiler level. Debuggers and validation tools are even less mature.

Application and user-related software

Application and user-related software cover everything with a direct interaction with the domain experts, such as programming APIs and libraries providing pre-defined elements. As a consequence of the previously mentioned limitations of the hardware technologies, a user-defined circuit must be transformed, often using algorithms based on linear algebra, into something that can run on the QPUs, compliant with their topology. This involves additional gates and ancilla qubits. This transformation is known as **transpilation**. To make QCs accessible to non-expert application developers there is a necessity for **user interfaces, libraries, high-level programming models and languages** as well as **compilers** which translate high level languages to quantum computing circuits, and transpilers which take care of the adaptation of already compiled circuits to a dedicated technology. Although some of these tools already exist in some form, the maturity level is quite low and additional developments will be needed when the system sizes of quantum computers increase.

System-related software

The system-related software is closely related to the system side of the QC, and the fine management of the compute resource provided by the QPUs. This leads to a classical schema where a computational task must be submitted to a limited and expensive computing resource. This kind of situation has already been addressed in the HPC world, and it requires **scheduling** mechanisms to operate properly. An efficient scheduler must handle waiting queues fairly and will optimize the usage of the related resource. Multi-level schedulers need to take care of the different time restrictions that occur in a hybrid QCS program (e.g. between shots, iterations, offloaded tasks). To this end, the definition of a standardized approach, which takes into account the different characteristics of each type of quantum hardware, such as the sampling rate, qubit connectivity and qubit number, among others, is required.

Using an expensive resource means that it will be necessary to “bill” it: this requires the QPUs to precisely account the use of the resource via documented and published metrics. As **accounting** is involved, the system management needs to know who made use of the resource and should be billed for this. This requires a precise and robust **authentication mechanism**. Another important point to be considered is **monitoring**, which influences the scheduling.

This “triumvirat” grouping authentication, accounting and scheduling already exists in the HPC software stack. QC middleware should leverage this work and should make sure that it can be easily integrated in this previously existing framework.

The explicit dichotomy between user-related and system-related middleware makes it necessary to explicitly define the interface. Standards are currently emerging, such as OpenQASM¹ and QRI², but no explicit consensus has chosen one format or another at the time of writing this text.

¹ Quantum ASsMbly Language, or QASM, is an open-source language used to describe quantum program at a very low level, in analogy to CPU assembly language. It has evolved as OpenQASM with its later versions, under the terms of the Apache 2.0 licence.

System integration

The overall efficiency of hybrid workflows is dependent on reducing the latency between the quantum and classical steps.

In the past years, cloud-based access has been established as one of the major business models of commercial quantum computing providers. Such solutions mean that most of the QCS-HPC integration (if existing) is a black box beyond the control of the user community. In Europe there is a focus on deploying QCS systems at the public HPC centres, which allows for a customized approach. The integration on infrastructure level means that interconnection networks and connectivity between HPC and QCS systems or emulators on hardware and protocol level need to be defined. Different quantum technologies need different interfaces. It is however desirable to have a hardware-agnostic middleware which could allow the programmers to benchmark different types of quantum devices. Furthermore, it is necessary to overcome both the different levels of maturity between HPC and QCS technologies and the incompatibility between their software stacks, since HPC is usually based on C++/Fortran while QCS are usually based on interpreted languages, such as Python.

Moreover, there are several initiatives in Europe to develop hybrid Quantum-HPC scheduling policies that take into account two challenges: the scarcity of quantum resources and their intrinsic difference with classical resources.

In most European HPC centres the deployment of QCS is happening right now and it is likely that this area of research needs some time to mature and might need additional research for new quantum systems to deploy.

² Quantum Intermediate Representation is standard supported by Microsoft and the QIR Alliance to represent a quantum program. QIR aims to provide a higher level of representation.

Emulation of quantum computers with HPC systems

Emulation is crucial for both current and future quantum computing software development. The life cycle begins with noiseless emulation to verify algorithms, proceeds to noisy emulation for preparing deployment on real machines, and culminates in hardware runs. HPC is instrumental in the design and noise modelling of emulators. Supercomputers are essential for emulating large QPUs due to their vast storage and parallel computing capabilities. Emulators can either simulate an ideal QPU with perfect coherence and fidelity or a realistic QC. This dual capability makes emulators indispensable for designing, analysing, and benchmarking quantum algorithms, as well as studying new qubit technologies. They are vital for developing new quantum computing applications, helping to validate algorithm behaviour without the non-idealities of current QCs, which, although being technologically advanced, are limited by noise.

Recent years have seen the development of different emulators, particularly software-based, GPU-based, and FPGA-based. Software-based emulators use methods like decision diagram-based simulators to reduce memory needs by finding patterns in state vectors and quantum gates. GPU-based emulators use Single-Instruction-Multiple-Data (SIMD) techniques to increase parallel processing in matrix operations necessary for quantum circuit simulation. FPGA-based emulators also use SIMD techniques and special designs to make the most of the sparse nature of gate matrices, cutting down on unnecessary operations and processing time. Even with these improvements, scalability is still limited by memory and execution time, leading to the use of modern HPC systems to simulate large quantum systems to overcome the exponential cost of these simulations. The largest simulation of a quantum circuit has been using 0.5 Petabytes to simulate 45 Qubits [T. Häner and D. S. Steiger, "0.5 Petabyte Simulation of a 45-Qubit

Quantum Circuit," *SC17: International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis*, Denver, CO, USA, 2017, pp. 1-10.].

In the future, emulators will remain important for refining quantum computing models. Unlike real QCs, emulators allow step-by-step analysis of quantum algorithms with high accuracy, including phase information. Emulators with noise models are also valuable for engineering new quantum technologies, as they provide performance insights by varying physical parameters. Moreover, emulators enable tracing the state of the circuit at any point for debugging, which is not possible on actual QPUs.

Most available emulators, although being open-source, are developed by QC manufacturers and often lack support for HPC implementations like distributed computing and GPU acceleration. Developing a fully parallel, accelerated (open-source) emulator is key to the rapid adoption of quantum technologies.

R&I priorities

In general, care should be taken to ensure that a holistic approach is taken in the early stages of QC hardware and software stack development, so that requirements of all layers of the stack are taken into account. Some parts of HPC-QCS integration can take advantage of previous developments in the HPC domain and start therefore from a higher TRL level than other parts. The recommendations for R&I priorities are in detail the following:

- Make sure that applications are considered in hardware-software co-design as well as any testing of middleware approaches in order to check that the requirements from the applications are taken into account.
- Facilitate a thriving open-source software stack to make sure that European hardware approaches and applications with quantum advantage are supported.
- Application oriented benchmarking is important to be able to evaluate the quality of quantum systems, both for internal comparisons and for comparison with classical algorithms.
- Authentication, accounting and scheduling mechanisms that are well-proven in HPC environments need to be adapted and integrated in the HPC-QC stack.
- For the design of the middleware a holistic approach needs to be taken into account, considering the application and the hardware requirements as well as the interface between system software and application and user related software.
- Emulators, supported by HPC infrastructures, are essential for validating and refining quantum algorithms and technologies for both today's noisy quantum computers and future advancements, as they ensure accurate simulations of the state vector evolution independent of quantum computer capabilities.

In addition to the more specific technical recommendations, the more general recommendations of the European Quantum Flagship SRIA are supported, especially:

- **HPC-QC middleware:** start to integrate and/or extend conventional HPC software stack components; support the development of HPC-QCS integration technology (connectivity, middleware, and libraries); initiate developments to create open-source middleware, schedulers, compilers, and other open-source software tools, where necessary think about software standards or contributing to them; support the development of software components, tools, runtimes and environments;
- **Applications:** support the development of scientific software applications;
- **Community Engagement:** engage the HPC and QCS communities; develop training mechanisms; contribute to the definition and emergence of global standards.

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